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THE STUDY OF IMPACT OF PRINCIPAL SCHOOL CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AMONG JOB EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

The role of school principal is significant in the achievement of school. The key responsibility of school principals are mission, vision, quality policy, academic success, establishing reputation, managing people, process, continuous improvement and making environment hospitable to learning process. In the present study attempt is made to investigate school principal conflict management strategies and its impact on job effectiveness on senior secondary school teachers. In the present study factorial research design is used. Two hypothesis and research question was framed to guide the study. Total 364 senior secondary school teachers participated in the present study. Tool used to collect data, were Senior Secondary School Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (SSTJEQ) and Principal Conflict Management Strategies (PCMSAQ). Research hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Result of the study shows that senior secondary school teachers job effectiveness level is very high. The application of conflict strategies by school principal has positive impact on senior secondary school teachers. Recommendations are made based on the findings.

Keywords: Principal; Conflict Management; Effectiveness; Teachers.

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1. Introduction

The education is universal practice through which societies are involved at all stages of development. The objective of education is to strengthen the individuals, nurture society, problem solving capabilities, ability. Education is for economic and social development. It is panacea to reduced poverty, improve health and promote democracy. In order to acquire the truth of education the role of educational leaders are extremely important in managing conflict practices in educational institutions.

The poor understanding of new paradigm underlying and dynamic transformation and poor adoption in work style among schoolteachers are the main cause of conflict. The communication barrier, not clear expectation, unclear rule, conflicting interest, unresolved past conflict, content issues are some of sources that leads to the conflict situation in school. The disagreements between people are due to scarce resources, difference in values and inconsistent teaching. The conflict may also arise when there is collision of real interest. This collision may be due to divergence in personal arbitration and organizational goal. The source of conflict can be personal and organizational level. In 21st century conflict is assumed to be a natural part of modern organization. It is the foundation of problem-solving skills and decision-making skills. The conflict will persist where incompatible difference exists.

Conflict can be significant and beneficial. Conflict can be beneficial as it is an indicator of problem and warning sign for potential problem. The conflict generated because of incompatible interest between groups, organization and peoples of diverse attitude, opinion, motives and outlook with any organization.

Conflict has potential of great deal of creativity, positive social change or distraction. Hence it is essential to understand foundation and basic process of conflict to maximized productive outcome and minimized distractions. The major cause of lowering quality education is conflict between school principal and teacher. The conflicts are realities in our school system because schools are organization where leaders and peoples to be lead are almost in equal qualification.

The dissatisfaction among teachers, multi-tasking staff, unnecessary dominating principals, dissatisfying appraisal and evaluation system, inappropriate distribution of class load are the reasons for conflict. Two elements are essential for conflicts ie., incompatibility views and divergent views.

Kroon(1991) conflict is observed as experience mismatched difference within individual or between two or more individuals which lead to some or other terms of disapproval.

Stoner(1991) conflict is disagreement about the allocation of scarce resources a clashes regarding goals, values and so on., can occur on interpersonal or organization level.

Slabbarl (1987) conflict as a dynamic process of interaction between two or more people or groups competing for rare resources, whose conflict objectives needs to have inconvincible strands.

The conflict management is what we do when we identify, deal with conflicting reasonable manner. To manage conflict negation and communication skills are required. The conflict management strategies ever expanding umbrella used to cover broad spectrum of approaches. It is the life skills, meditations skills and negotiation skills.

The aim of conflict management is to achieve constructive emotional state in all parties, a clear, mutual understanding of others views. The management of the conflict required interpersonal process, group process, notice tension, began to listen, summarized other views, state your views, summarized both side. Identify needs versus beliefs.

School principal is responsible in the success of academics. The decisions taken by school principal have direct impact on school working culture. Teachers mostly complain that decisions affecting them are usually made without their knowledge and hence there is an urgent need to involve teachers in decision making process in departmental scheduling, students scheduling and duty assignments.

The school principal must be responsible for motivation, stimulation and encouragement activities that will foster improvement in teaching-learning. School principal is the driving force of school development. The opportunities are placed within the capacities of school. School principal is an important factor in effective and efficient monitoring; mentoring of school principal enables to influence others to accept his decision willingly and freely. The school principal has broad spectrum of role and function. The merit of quality education is to have quality school principle. School principal required extra ordinary qualities, traits, attitude, values, ethics, behavior and strong image.

School principal encountered with problems, difficulties which need attention. As school principal face problems, challenges as supervision and administrative role they make necessary adjustment to cope up with demand of role. The adaptation due to the challenges is essential.

2. Objectives of the Study

The objective of present study is to investigate school principal conflict management, strategies application and schoolteachers' job effectiveness in senior secondary schools of central India. The following objectives are framed to guide the study.

- 1) To investigate the level of job effectiveness among teachers in senior secondary schools.
- 2) To investigate impact of principal of arbitration, dialogue, effective communication on job of effectiveness of senior secondary school.

3. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are framed to guide the study.

- 1) Job effectiveness among teachers of senior secondary school is not significantly high.
- 2) The school principal application of communication, dialogue, arbitration, conflict management strategies have no significant impact on senior secondary school teachers.

4. Research Design

The factorial research design was employed.

Population

It comprised 1500 public senior secondary schools in 52 districts.

Sample

Total 364 senior secondary school teachers participated in the study. Purposive sampling technique is employed to draw the sample.

Tool

Two tools are used to collect the data for the present study. One is Senior Secondary School Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (SSTJEQ), it consists of total twenty items and were organized on a 4-point Likart scale and Principal Conflict Management Statistics Application Questionnaire (PCMWAQ), it consists of ten items on a 4-point scale. Test- re-test technique is used to attain reliability co-efficient value of 0.86. The copy of questionnaire was administrated to teachers on different teachers' during in-service teachers training programme. Partly- analyzed by using Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS).

5. Result

Table 1: Result of t-test of senior secondary school teachers job effectiveness:

Variable	Mean	μ	SD	SE	t-calculated	Sig
Job Effectiveness	6.92	24	2.242	.120	-147.01	.000

Sig at <0.05, df = 363, μ = test variables

Table 2: Multiple regression analysis of principal impact conflict statistics in senior secondary school teachers:

R	R-Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. error
.69	.28	0.22	2.212

Table 3: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) – Regression Analysis

Source	Df	SS	ms	F	Sig F
Regression	3	90.65	29.98	4.271	-0.0032
Residue	360	3019.81	6.25		
Total	363	3111.51			

Sig at $p < 0.05$

Table 4: Relative contribution of principal application of conflict management strategies:

Variables	Coefficient	SE	t-stat	Rank	p- value
Intercept	4.822	.242	8.37	4	0.00
Arbitration	0.95	.294	1.425	3	0.74
Dialogue	0.97	0.21	2.045	1	0.16
Positive Communication	0.72	0.85	1.75	2	0.33

Hypothesis (HO1)

Job effectiveness among teachers among senior secondary school is not significantly high. Result presented in Table-1 showed that p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significant at 363 degree of freedom. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis

The school principal conflict management statistics has no impact in senior secondary school teachers.

Table -2 shows multiple regressions analysis of three key conflict management strategies (such as effective communication, dialogue and arbitration) has positive impact on senior secondary school teacher job. Effectiveness ($R=169.6$). It shows the conflict management strategies used by school principal for job effectiveness is quiet relevant. These conflict management strategies explained 2.8% of total variance of job effectiveness of teachers ($R\text{ square}= 0.28$). The remaining 92% may be due to some other factors which are not covered in the present study.

Result presented in Table -3 shows clearly that R-square value obtained from regression analysis is statistically significant (p-value 0.02) less than that of 0.05 alpha level ($F= 0.830\%$, p value $0.02 < 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Result presented in Table-4 shows that out of three conflict management strategies practice by school principal has noteworthy influence on job effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers (p-value- $0.016, 0.74 > 0.05$). The dialogue (0.04) and effective communication (0.138) is effective and efficient strategies of conflict management but arbitration is not statistically significant.

6. Discussion

Result of the study shows that, first hypothesis of present study that senior secondary school teachers' job effectiveness is significantly high. It may be teachers are taking board classes and making deliberate efforts to improve students' academic performance. Teachers prepare notes, hand outs, introduce students to take part in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. Teachers identify and nurture hidden and latent talent among students.

Teachers makes efforts in students active participation in learning process, motivates students interest in learning and conceptual understanding. Result on study does not mean that teachers effectiveness is absolutely perfect but significant in job effectiveness among senior secondary school teachers. The result of the present study is in line with Ogoch (2014). The teachers shows positive attitude towards work.

The dialogue as a strategy of conflict management is most effective following positive communication and arbitration. Result of present study supports the findings of L. Mathew (2014) that conflict management strategies such as smoothing, dialogue, arbitration and effective communication has positive impact on senior secondary school teachers.

Arbitration as conflict management strategy is not effective. The findings of the study are not supporting the findings of Rathoure (2010). The study reveals that arbitration has positive impact on job effectiveness of teachers.

The result of the present study shows that dialogue as conflict management strategies has positive impact on teachers' effectiveness. This finding of the study collaborates with L. Mathew and Rathoure. Their study reveals that arbitration has significant impact on job satisfaction of senior

secondary school teachers. Fair, active listening, dignity, peaceful meeting, understanding others views, dispersing difference of opinion, association, recognition are few qualities of school principal which are effective and efficient in conflict management.

The positive communication is effective in conflict management strategies. Principal used meditation, communication, create supportive environment as effective conflict management strategies.

7. Conclusion

It was reasonably concluded that principals conflict management strategies has positive impact on teaches effectiveness. The job effectiveness in terms of the students academic performance, discipline, personality development, students participation in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. The teachers motivate students for active participation in learning process. The conflict management strategies of school principal boost the morale of teachers and their work effectively.

8. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are made to improve effectiveness of teachers.

- 1) Teachers must be provided with performance based values to motivate teachers to improve job effectiveness.
- 2) School should organize continuous seminar, workshops, conferences on effective conflict management.
- 3) Every school should have conflict management committee responsible for maintain teachers conflicts.
- 4) School principal should not allow personal inclination and interest to negatively influence their choice to resolve conflict management.
- 5) Teachers should be trained on behavioural management towards conflict resolving.
- 6) Teachers should have positive attitude to apologize to others. It will help to eliminate conflict.

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